

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO CHILDREN UP TO SCHOOL AGE

Rasulova Gulnoza Fayzullayevna

Senior lecturer of TDTU "Corporate management"

department Usmonov Sherali Tal'atjon o'g'li

TDTU MN-2 group student

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Abstract: this scientific article is called "Methods of teaching a foreign language to children of preschool age", several methods of interesting and meaningful teaching of English to children are mentioned. Today's world language is becoming English, so it should be started from preschool age.

Keywords: riddles, practical exercises, news, interesting games, brainstorming, brainstorming exercises, pedagogical techniques.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in the family, in public or in class. Knowledge of language phenomena is studied theoretically. It is known that teaching and learning a foreign language differs sharply from the mother tongue and other languages in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. Also, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Measures for the further improvement of the preschool education system" in 2017-2021 encourages the study of a foreign language. According to L. S. Vygotsky, children begin to learn their native language on their own, involuntarily, and they learn a foreign language consciously. That is why language learning skills are formed in children as follows: mother tongue develops from bottom to top, and foreign language develops from top to bottom. For the last several years, learning a foreign language has become a necessity for everyone, young and old. Nowadays, foreign language is becoming the main part of all educational institutions. The growing demand for foreign languages in our society does not ignore not only young people, but also parents. One of the main reasons for brain activity is the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. For example, it is very convenient for children up to school age. After all, children of this age are very curious and ambitious. That is, at this age, their memory is developing. Therefore, they are easy to remember. The purpose of teaching a foreign language to children of kindergarten age is as follows:

1) Formation of basic communication skills in a foreign language in young children.

2) To create a positive attitude towards learning foreign languages.

In learning foreign languages, teaching through games is also useful. Even the simplest sentences and phrases seem interesting to them. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them a foreign language in different ways. Then they will not get bored, they will learn with interest. For example, a child sits at a table and does not flip through a book, but takes everything literally and tries to speak in simple sentences. In my opinion, all this is through games.

It is necessary to use easy and understandable methods when teaching a foreign language to children of kindergarten age. For example, teaching a child using objects that surround him is an easy method. There are also several other methods. Before the lesson begins, if the teacher sings a nice English song and dances to the tune, the child will quickly memorize the words of the song. It is also correct to show foreign language cartoons to children of this age. It's true, you can say, how can a child understand a language if he doesn't know it. But even if the child does not understand, it will not be difficult for him to understand and understand through the actions of cartoon characters. In addition, the teacher should create an environment related to the subject. Let's take the topic of trip for example. The teacher will explain how to organize a trip for this, what means of travel (bus, boat, bicycle, train), where to travel (Kokand, Samarkand, Bukhara). A foreign language can be taught easily through various methods. For example, if you use the method of working with signs and pictures, the method of voice recognition and adaptation, and the method of adapting your activity to the students, you will not be mistaken. Now it is no exaggeration to say that the way of working through pictures and symbols is to translate from pictures to words. For example, according to Dr. Elaine Fogel Schneider, director of Touchtime International, about promoting daily vocabulary: "It's about verbally labeling children with common brands and symbols." He explains that picture-to-word translation helps with language development. That is, it greatly helps children learn new languages quickly and easily. As for how to tailor their activities to students, Gretzinger says children need to be more sensitive to children in non-traditional homes. Think twice before asking students to draw pictures of their family - think carefully about how an adopted child might feel as an alienated child and how other children might react to them. Engaging in inclusive activities can take some time, especially at the beginning of the year, because teachers do not have information about children, that is, they do not know about their lifestyle and family. At the same time, the information acquired

through the medium of a foreign language and the intellectual and speech skills and abilities acquired during the study of the English language educate children.

Teaching language to young children is not without obligation, but if it is done in a fun and interesting way, it will not be without benefits. Of course, a language learner can also learn a language out of interest. Learning foreign languages opens the door to new opportunities for the young generation in the future, we need to make our contribution so that they become qualified personnel and become useful people for the whole society. That is why children should be educated from a young age. We need to make them interested in reading, not to forget every child, to spend special time with children who are difficult to master, and to encourage them while teaching foreign languages. In addition, the use of several effective methods will further develop the child's interest in a foreign language.

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